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Human-Nature Relationship in Tagore's Selected Short Stories: A Perspective on Posthuman Ecology

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Abstract:

The objective of this research paper is to find the presentations of nature, human beings and their relationship with one another in the short stories of R.N.Tagore. The short stories under discussion present different ways of presentation of nature with respect to human beings. An attempt has been made to make a comparative analysis and explore how nature in Tagore's short stories, "Hungry Stone" and "The Home-coming", depicting the significance of inclusion of Nature's flora and fauna, the greeneries, and the natural environment in the domain of human existence, differs in the above stories. Anthropocentrism is questioned in both the South Asian short stories. Theoretical concept of posthuman-ecocriticism has been used in this study for examining the comparative roles of human beings and the natural environment. This study uses a content analysis method and the study reveals that human beings are affected by nature differently under varied circumstances and situations.

Keywords: Ecocriticism, rivers, environment, anthropocentrism, comparative aesthetics, nature.

The selected short stories exhibit a subtle human-nature bonding that the anthropocentric human civilization has long been ignoring and attempting to push to subdue it. Tagore's short stories depict the significance of inclusion of Nature's flora and fauna, the greeneries, and the natural environment in the domain of human existence. Tagore's concern on environmental exploitation and breach of human-nature bonding is reflected in his literature. The short stories highlight Tagore's thoughts of the importance of protecting Nature without which human beings become drastically alienated and suffer the horrible apocalyptic end that may not find ways of any reversible effect in the future. Tagore's works included here address the intensity of the emotional attachment of the characters and dissolves the human-nature binary and the dualistic treatment of living and the non-living. Tagore's extensive work reveals an intrinsic view where all the experiences of the world are found to be, not isolated from the experiences of nature but, to seek a way of human development that includes a posthumanist outlook that can maintain a harmony and uphold a balance of human-nature relationship without which none can exist. "Ecology is a science strongly connected to a history of verbal expression" (Howarth 71). Posthumanism and Ecology, both connected with the human and the environment decentres anthropocentrism.

Tagore's short story, "The Home-coming", is a heart rendering tale of an adolescent boy, Phatik who is a very jolly and playful young boy of the village. He enjoys all the bliss that nature offers. He plays with his playmates, fights with them and other opposing groups of boys and even with his little brother, makes pranks with juniors and peers, laughs, cries, screams and what not. But it is interesting to note that he does all these in the lap of nature. He and his co-mates are born and brought up in the lap of nature. They are all intricately associated with nature, the surrounding environment and the blessings of nature:

“Phatik Chakravorti was ringleader among the boys of the village. A new mischief got into his head. There was a heavy log lying on the mud-flat of the river waiting to be shaped into a mast for a boat. He decided that they should all work together to shift the log by main force from its place and roll it away. The owner of the log would be angry and surprised, and they would all enjoy the fun” (Tagore 1).

The village boys are depicted to have a very close association with Nature. They are mischievous, prank-loving and playful in their dealings with nature and the environment. The river mentioned in the short story has become a common and everyday-life entity that takes part in the playful activities of the little boys of the village. They are not afraid of the river as the river seems to have a close association with them. They play and fight, quarrel and enjoy - all together under the open sky, keeping their foot on the same ground and in the same level of all the boundaries, existing in their little young aged lives. Phatik, along with his friends played a prank with Makhan, his younger brother and rolled the log along with Makhan who opposed his idea of rolling down the log from its assigned place:

“His fertile brain, however, rapidly seized upon a new maneuver which would discomfit his brother and afford his followers an added amusement. He gave the word of command to roll the log and Makhan over together. But he overlooked the fact, like those who attempt earthly fame in other matters, that there was peril in it” (Tagore 1).

Playing with logs and the elements of nature was an everyday affair of those playful little boys. They laugh, cry, scream and fight but nature and the environment are always intertwined with them. The river is always associated with them and it plays a vital role in the lives of the village people and the village boys there. Rosi Braidotti in *More Posthuman Glossary* (2022) observes, “The tendency to flatten out structural inequalities and systemic discrimination is manifest in moves towards the non-human that displace epistemology but avoid issues of power and social justice” (30). Phatik finds solace in his mind and his fright

against the grudges of his mother subside when he turns to the village river. He spends lone hours sitting near the village river:

“Phatik wiped his face, and sat down on the edge of a sunken barge by the river bank, and began to chew a piece of grass” (Tagore 1).

The natural environment, the river and the village atmosphere was very congenial for Phatik and his playmates. They adapted very well with nature and nature was a part of their life. The river, a representative of nature, was also an important means of communication. It served as a good connector between the city and the village. The river allowed the village people to earn their livelihood from it. Communication through boats was another important part in the lives of the villagers. People from other regions and cities also maintained their communication through boats:

“A boat came up to the landing and a middle-aged man, with gray hair and dark mustache, stepped on shore. He saw the boy sitting there doing nothing and asked him where the Chakravortis lived. Phatik went chewing the grass and said: “Over there,” but it was quite impossible to tell where he pointed. The stranger asked him again. He swung his legs to and fro on the side of the barge and said: “Go and find out,” and continued to chew the grass as before” (Tagore 1).

With the setting of foot of the new man in Phatik's village, a new phase of life begins in the life of the village boy for whom nature was his second mother. The appearance of the apparently strange man brings strange changes in Phatik's orientation towards life. The strange man is a stranger to nature's bounty and the blessings ushered by nature. He belongs to the city and is accustomed to the city -life. He fails to appreciate nature's close association with the village people. The strange man is none other than Bishamber babu, Phatik's maternal uncle who lives in the city in Calcutta. He appears as a stranger because he does not visit his married sister in her house frequently. He himself does not recognise his own

nephew, Phatik. The suggestion hits the doubt that this is the first time he is seeing Phatik. The boundary of kinship between the brother and the sister is blurred once the sister is married off. Bishamber babu is quite unaware about his two nephews, Phatik and Makhan. In the same way, Phatik and Makhan have not seen their maternal uncle, Bishamber babu and consequently, he appears stranger to them. The spell is broken only when Phatik's mother recognizes Bishamber babu and touches his feet, addressing him as her brother:

“But when his mother stepped back and looked at the stranger, her anger was changed to surprise. For she recognised her brother, and cried: “Why, Dada! Where have you come from?”As she said these words, she bowed to the ground and touched his feet. Her brother had gone away soon after she had married, and he had started business in Bombay. His sister had lost her husband while he was in Bombay. Bishamber had now come back to Calcutta, and had at once made enquiries about his sister. He had then hastened to see her as soon as he found out where she was” (Tagore 2).

The stranger blurs the boundary of strangeness and tries to become one of them. Gradually, he gets to know about all the nuances of Phatik but expresses his wish to take Phatik with him to Calcutta and take the responsibility of his education:

“The brother asked after the education of the two boys. He was told by his sister that Phatik was a perpetual nuisance. He was lazy, disobedient, and wild. But Makhan was as good as gold, as quiet as a lamb, and very fond of reading, Bishamber kindly offered to take Phatik off his sister's hands, and educate him with his own children in Calcutta. The widowed mother readily agreed” (Tagore 2).

Bishamber babu hoped to blur and erase the boundary of otherness. He wanted to keep Phatik in the same level as that of his own sons. But he fails to realize that the boy, so close to nature, would not thrive in the claustrophobic city atmosphere. Moreover, he fails to realize

that it was impossible to wipe out and replace the bond of Phatik with his own mother. Never can a mother be replaced by another lady who is not his or her real mother:

“For a boy of fourteen his own home is the only Paradise. To live in a strange house with strange people is little short of torture, while the height of bliss is to receive the kind looks of women, and never to be slighted by them” (Tagore 3).

Besides, the village, its surrounding natural environment and the river associated with it had become mingled with the temperament of Phatik. Graham Huggan and Helen Tiffin also observed, “for Adorno in particular, as for several other philosophers of modernity, alienation is the price human beings have paid for their increasing control and management of nature” (203). Phatik's coming to the city was like cutting his bonds with nature. He was a son of mother -Nature. Consequently, the boundaries created by his dwelling village and the city of Calcutta remained prominent and could not be blurred when he started living in the city:

“The cramped atmosphere of neglect in his aunt's house oppressed Phatik so much that he felt that he could hardly breathe. He wanted to go out into the open country and fill his lungs and breathe freely. But there was no open country to go to. Surrounded on all sides by Calcutta houses and walls, he would dream night after night of his village home, and long to be back there. He remembered the glorious meadow where he used to fly his kite all day long; the broad river-banks where he would wander about the livelong day singing and shouting for joy; the narrow brook where he could go and dive and swim at any time he liked. He thought of his band of boy companions over whom he was despot; and, above all, the memory of that tyrant mother of his, who had such a prejudice against him, occupied him day and night. A kind of physical love like that of animals; a longing to be in the presence of the one who is loved; an inexpressible wistfulness during absence; a silent cry of the inmost heart for the mother, like the lowing of a calf in the twilight;-this love, which was almost an animal

instinct, agitated the shy, nervous, lean, uncouth and ugly boy. No one could understand it, but it preyed upon his mind continually” (Tagore 3-4).

Phatik longed to go back to his village home but there was no way out. His maternal uncle could take him back only when his school would have long holidays in the month of November and that was too long for him. The atmosphere in his maternal house and also in his school gradually turned to be unbearable for him. He was teased by his fellow mates, thrashed by his teachers and his aunt showed annoyance with him in the house. He turned nostalgic. Days and nights he thought only of his days in his village home. The open outstretched sky over his head, fresh air to breathe in, the river, his jolly playmates, his younger brother and his mother- all seemed to call him back to his own village. The boundary of limitation, created by the city life in Calcutta, was getting blurred by the memories of his village home and the environment surrounding it. The physical reality was diluted and the boundary between the present real world of the city and the past nostalgic memories of the village were constantly getting blurred in the mind of Phatik. He returned home with high fever:

“That night, on his way back from school, Phatik had a bad headache with a fit of shivering. He felt he was going to have an attack of malarial fever. His one great fear was that he would be a nuisance to his aunt” (Tagore 4).

While discussing on what posthumanism does Herbrechter observed, “it looks closely at the idea that something like “nature” can be clearly distinguished from “culture” or “society,” that a “self” and “identity” might be separated from the effects of “otherness” and “difference,” that a “body” might be extracted from its “environ-ment,” or that there might be a strict dividing line between “subject” and “object” (8). Nature’s call was stronger than the call of the city-life. Phatik began to resist the city-people as he did not receive the warmth of

a harmonious relation of care, affection and love. Fearing his aunt's wrath, Phatik tried to flee from the house but finally got rescued by police the next evening:

"The fever rose very high, and all that night the boy was delirious. Bishamber brought in a doctor. Phatik opened his eyes flushed with fever, and looked up to the ceiling, and said vacantly: "Uncle, have the holidays come yet? May I go home?" (Tagore 4).

The next day the doctor announced that Phatik's condition was very critical. Nature left such an imprint in Phatik's mind that he remembers his village and the river he lived nearby. He babbled in his severe feverish condition and the memories of his village days, the village environment, nature and the river hovered over his mind constantly:

"Phatik began to cry out; "By the mark! --three fathoms. By the mark-- four fathoms. By the mark-." He had heard the sailor on the river- steamer calling out the mark on the plumb-line. Now he was himself plumbing an unfathomable sea" (Tagore 5).

He remembers the river and its unfathomable depth. His subconscious mind becomes stronger and nature takes its control over the conscious mind of Phatik. The subconscious mind starts to recognize the supreme power of nature that the conscious mind of Phatik had rejected and lured him to the city life that had overcrowded sky with tall buildings, no green meadow to play and run about on it, no touch of the reality he had expected before landing onto the city. Finally, Phatik breathes his last, imagining a return to his village home across the river. Phatik, the child of nature returns to his village, though not physically but in the figment of his imagination. Kroker observed, "And over time, as codes of law sought to control violence within groups, so did philosophers and clerics and statesmen seek to regulate the destructive power of war"(129). Here Phatik's war was with himself and the unfavourable environment where he was thrust into. The short story is a journey of Phatik where he judges the power relations between the city life, the man-made civilization and the village life, that

represents nature and its purest form of civilization. The boundary between the conscious mind and the subconscious mind of Phatik gradually gets blurred and he fails to recognize the real world and the world of his imagination. In his deathbed, Phatik erases the boundary between the city-life and the village-life. Evidently, he, as a child of nature seeks the abolition, erasure and blurring of the boundaries of man-made binaries and confinements called city and village. He seems to include and embrace the man-made city within the domain of nature and embrace a uniform world, and thereby bring a uniformity in the natural world where human beings and nature can cohabit peacefully and protect each other, without human being's exploitation of nature. Jackson observed, "We suggest that approaches to coloniality can learn from posthumanisms. Posthumanisms can learn from postcolonial and decolonising efforts. It is in the learning, and so in grappling with the difficult questions that arise for each, that we might be able to think, and so act, carefully towards the many pressing demands of our contemporary moment" (6).

Tagore's short story, "Hungry Stone" focuses on an aspect of nature which is very much different from the usual environmental aspect of nature. Though the story includes Nature and environmental aspects like river, mountain, forests, rain and fountain, the functional aspect of Nature is very different in the sense that it focuses on the sensuous aspects and its sensuous effect on human beings. The Nature and environment, presented in "Hungry Stone" blurs the boundary of the ordinary concept of nature that exists as a part of the planet, earth.

Oftentimes, a natural entity, in the short story assumes the role of a nimble lady and in other times, Nature becomes hungry like a monster. Nature changes its shape and alters their roles, in the mind of the narrator. It is important to note that all the major incidents happening in the short story are products of the imagination of the first person narrator of the short story. The unique experiences of the narrator begin only when the boundary of the real world blurs and

imagination creeps into his dream world. Barich is the town and Shusta is the river where the incidents, connected with Nature occur:

“Barich stands upon a very romantic site. Beneath a range of lonely mountains, the fast-flowing river, Shusta (from the Sanskrit *svachchhatoa*, limpid) runs like a nimble dancer through towering forests along its winding, rippling course. Right on its banks, looming in solitude at the foot of the mountains, at the top of a flight of one hundred and fifty stone steps, rises a palace building of white marble” (Chaudhuri 136).

In the short story, Nature and natural environment along with its isolation evoked an imaginative world in the mind of the narrator. His real world blurred and mingled with the imaginative world. In his imaginative world, Nature and its natural setting gave him the impression of the presence of a bevy of young ladies, running down a flight of one hundred fifty steps down to the river Shusta. It appeared to the narrator that the invisible ladies splattered water upon one another in the river which was flowing in a low stream. The river, a representative of nature, blurs its own boundary and becomes a nimble dancer, a human being in the mind's eye of the narrator:

“The moment the sun slipped below the mountain-top, a low dark curtain descended upon the stage of the day. Because the hilly terrain shut out the last light of the sun, twilight was of short duration here. Toying with the idea of going for a ride, I had half-risen from my chair when I heard a footstep on the steps behind me. I turned to look: there was no one there.

My hearing had played a trick on me, I decided; but no sooner had I sat down than I heard a sound again, a number of footsteps this time, running quickly down the stairs. I was transfixed, seized by an excited delight not unmixed with a tinge of fear. There was nothing in front of me, no discernable form; yet I knew, as well as if I could see them, that a group of high-spirited young women had just stepped into the river to bathe at the end of the hot

summer's day. Even though there was not so much as a whisper anywhere that evening, neither in the mountains, the river nor the house, I still heard the bathers perfectly clearly as they swept past me one after another, laughing and chattering like a playful mountain stream" (Chaudhuri 137).

The functional aspect of Nature blurs the boundary of the common notion of environment as Nature becomes an agent of sensuous catalyst in the story. Nature in different shades and different forms assumes the role of human beings, in the short story, "Hungry Stone":

"The river was as calm as ever, but I still felt clearly that the waters were being stirred by many braceleted arms, as the women laughed and splashed water on each other, and their feet sent the water drops arcing through the air like fistful of pearls" (Chaudhuri 137).

Greg Garrard has quoted Sharon Doubiago's words, "ecology consciousness is traditional women consciousness" (27). The strange environment of the place at Barich wiped out its real natural existence and thrust back the narrator to a past time of Mahmud Shah. In such a blurred time-frame, the narrator visualized some snow-white ladies in saffron pajamas with her two exquisite feet dangling on the red carpet of the floor and also could he smell the scent of attar. The haunted atmosphere and the precarious natural setting blurred the real self of the narrator and made him feel the cry and mourning of deserted women, asking to be rescued by him. Nature and environment imposed such forces on the anthropocentric world that the real self and the real identity of the human narrator got blurred. Nature is beyond the grasp of human beings in terms of its power and magnitude. Nature is beyond human beings, and it is post-human in its approach towards human beings.

"Suddenly the pall of stillness was swept aside by a gust of wind. The Shusta's surface was quickly teased into wavelets, like the braids of a heavenly nymph, and the shadowy evening forest gave a deep sigh, as if waking from a bad dream. Dream or reality, the unseen mirage

from two hundred and fifty years ago that had presented itself before me vanished in the twinkling of an eye. The magical creatures that had brushed past me with swift disembodied steps and shrill silent laughter to plunge into the Shusta did not make their way back, wringing the water from their dripping clothes. They vanished in that single breath of spring, as a whiff of perfume is lost upon the breeze" (Chaudhuri 138).

Nature casted a spell on the lone human narrator and decentred his autonomy by reducing him to the position of an object on which the star, an embodiment of Nature could cast a glance. The star, the sky and the galaxies assumed subjecthood in Tagore's short story, "Hungry Stone" as the human narrator surrendered himself to the objects and entities of Nature:

"A brilliant star shone through an open window: perched high above the dark forested Aravalli mountains, from its exalted place in the sky millions of leagues away, it fixed its gaze upon the humble Mr Tax-Collector on his humble camp-cot. Diverted by this odd conceit, I soon drifted off to sleep: for how long I cannot say, but suddenly I felt myself shiver, and I was awake again. It was not as though there had been any sound in the room, or that anyone had entered it. But by that time, the dim glow of the waning moon was creeping in diffidently through the open window, while the star that had gazed so fixedly upon me had dipped beneath the gloomy mountains" (Chaudhuri 139-40).

A tension was created between the waking mind of the human narrator and his subconscious self that found expression in his dreams. He was engulfed by the illusion, desire and supernatural outcome within a natural context. He lost himself to the Natural world and was only shocked to return back from his dream world and embark into the world of reality by the intervention of a human call:

“I started at the sound of a piercing shout, and found myself sitting on my camp-cot, drenched in sweat. The waning moon had turned pale in the first light of dawn, like a sick man after a sleepless night; and crazy old Meher Ali was marching down the empty road as was his custom, shouting, ‘Stay away, stay away’” (Chaudhuri 141).

The human narrator narrator was so entranced by the mysteries of Nature that he amalgamated his imaginative human laughter and melody with the rustling sound of the swirling dry leaves from the nearby Aravalli mountain. The wind, the air and the rough windy storm made appearance in such a way that they appeared to be mightier than the human speaker and obstructed his evening outing by snatching his hat and court:

“One evening, I thought of going out for a ride. I have no idea who it was that kept dissuading me, but I paid no heed. My sola-topee and short jacket were hanging from a wooden rack. Just as I was about to change into them, a sudden whirlwind swept down, carrying the sand of the Shusta and dead leaves from the Aravallis like a pennant, and bore away my jacket and my hat. They went cart-wheeling through the air: a sweet chorus of laughter swirled along with them, rising through several octaves, sounding every note on the scale of derision, until finally it dissolved into the sunset” (Chaudhuri 142).

In Tagore’s short story, “Hungry Stone” Nature has blurred its boundary and become one with the human beings. The floor of the marble palace screamed like a captivated lady who yearned liberation. The fountains in the marble palace woke up from their deep sleep of the centuries past and began to sprout on their own. The whole marble palace became alive like a living organism and became involved with the human’s activities and intervened in the human narrator’s thought process:

“That very midnight, sitting up suddenly on my bed, I heard the sound of weeping- racing, broken-hearted sobs. It was as though beneath my bed, beneath the floor, among the

foundations of this vast mass of stone, a voice was calling out from a dark and musty grave, crying: 'Take me away, give me my deliverance; break down the doors of this rooted illusion, this deep sleep, this futile dream. Put me on your horse, take me in your embrace- carry me away through the forest, over the mountains, across the river into your own sunlit room. Give me my deliverance!'" (Chaudhuri 142-43).

"Humanism's restricted notion of what counts as the human is one of the keys to understand how we got to a post-human turn at all" (Braidotti 16). The narrator in the short story, "Hungry Stone" goes beyond the conceptual portrayal of human being. He extends his understanding of the boundaries that limited a human being. He sees human being in the form of Nature. The human narrator finds Nature mimicking human being. The approaching storm has been invested with human attributes when the distant forests have been depicted to be howled like a mad man. The howling storm rolling across the surrounding place has been depicted as a mad man who has broken his chains to set himself free. The thunders have been depicted as to be something like the flashing teeth of the mad man. The human narrator thus pictured a human- face in the canvas of Nature's surroundings. Human being and Nature often interchanged their places and swiped their positions as subjects and objects of gaze in Tagore's short story, "Hungry Stone":

"Then, suddenly, I felt a couple of teardrops falling on my cheek. The sky above the Aravallis had been heavy with rain-filled clouds that day. The darkness-shrouded forest and the Shusta's inky waters were still with fearful expectation. Suddenly, the water, the earth and the sky quivered, all at once; and a howling storm burst forth out of the distant forest like a madman that had burst his chains, baring its teeth in lighting-flashes. The palace's empty cavernous rooms began to shriek in torment, beating their doors wildly in the wind" (Chaudhuri 144).

“Right then, in the pouring rain, I ran up to the crazy old fellow and asked: ‘Meher Ali, what is it that’s a lie?’

He thrust me aside without an answer and went on his way, circling around and around in a mesmeric trance, like a bird caught in the hypnotic spell of a python’s gaze” (Chaudhuri 145).

The blurring of boundaries between the human and Nature, the living and nonliving, and finally the human and divine in Tagore’s works relate to the posthuman approach in a multilayered interplay where nature dissolves and amalgamates into a melting pot with all inclusive creator and cosmos with the all encompassing and richly filled biodiverse planet we live in. Terry Gifford aptly remarked, “much pastoral poetry begins with awe but leans towards comfort and complacency” (58). Tagore’s “Hungry Stone” retreats back to the pastoral world.

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